

Automated Lesion Segmentation in Whole-Body PET/CT: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

Automated Lesion Segmentation in Whole-Body PET/CT

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

autoPET V

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Positron emission tomography (PET) combined with computed tomography (CT) plays a central role in oncologic staging, response assessment, and disease monitoring. Currently, diagnostic assessment is performed by radiologists (i.e. human observers) on PET/CT scans through the detection of changes in tumour size and distribution using standardised criteria. Despite the highly time-consuming nature of this manual task, only unidimensional (diameter) evaluations of a subset of tumour lesions are used to assess tumour dynamics. Additional quantitative evaluation of PET information would potentially allow for more precise and individualized diagnostic decisions. Besides the risk of inter-observer variability, the manual approach only extracts a diminutive proportion of the morphologic tumour data derived from images, thereby neglecting valuable, significant, and prognostic information.

Automation of tumour detection and segmentation may enable faster and more comprehensive information and data extraction. While recent editions of the autoPET challenge series have demonstrated substantial progress in automated whole-body lesion segmentation across tracers and centers, persistent challenges remain. These include sensitivity to domain shifts, physiological tracer uptake mimicking disease, complex lesion phenotypes, and the resulting limited alignment between fully automated segmentations and clinical expectations. In clinical practice, lesion segmentation will therefore not be a static, fully automated task, but a dynamic interpretive process in which human expertise remains essential.

autoPET V addresses this gap by introducing a unified benchmark for interactive, clinician-in-the-loop lesion segmentation in whole-body PET/CT. Participants are tasked with developing algorithms that iteratively refine lesion segmentations in response to sparse corrective input, represented as scribbles targeting false positives and false negatives. The challenge evaluates a single task under two complementary interaction regimes using scribbles: a standardized simulated-interaction setting that enables scalable and reproducible benchmarking, and a clinician-driven interaction setting based on real expert input that captures realistic human-AI correction

behavior. All submissions are evaluated under both regimes and are eligible for corresponding award categories.

A second pillar of autoPET V is a fully new, harmonized, multi-center test cohort spanning diverse tracers, scanners, disease burdens, and a substantial fraction of lesion-absent studies. Building on lessons learned from previous autoPET editions and related challenges, including DeepPSMA, PET quantification is harmonized following QIBA-aligned SUV normalization procedures to improve cross-site comparability. Evaluation metrics are revised to better disentangle semantic tumor burden estimation from instance-level lesion delineation and to assess not only final segmentation quality but also adaptation efficiency over interaction steps.

To support reproducibility and broad participation, autoPET V is accompanied by structured onboarding materials, including Jupyter notebook tutorials, example data loaders, and detailed task descriptions illustrating interactive segmentation workflows and the representation of corrective scribbles. In addition, a moderated question-and-answer forum facilitates clarification of best practices established in previous autoPET editions. These resources are designed to lower the technical entry barrier while promoting transparent and comparable algorithm development.

Overall, autoPET V aims to advance PET/CT AI beyond static automation toward robust, adaptive, and clinically meaningful human-AI collaboration.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

PET/CT, tumor, lesion, segmentation, interactive segmentation

Year

2026

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

AutoPET V introduces a conceptual shift from static, fully automated lesion segmentation toward dynamic, interactive, clinician-in-the-loop PET/CT analysis, reflecting how tumor burden is assessed in real clinical workflows. While previous editions of the autoPET challenge focused on robustness across tracers, centers, and imaging conditions, autoPET V is the first in the series to explicitly frame lesion segmentation as an adaptive process, in which algorithms must respond efficiently and robustly to sparse human guidance.

In this context, the dynamic setting refers to inference-time integration of corrective input, where models update their predictions based on scribbles without retraining or parameter optimization between interaction steps. This may include architectures that condition predictions on interaction masks, prompt-based mechanisms, memory-aware refinement modules, or other interaction-aware inference strategies. The challenge does not prescribe a specific implementation paradigm but evaluates how effectively corrective input is incorporated within a fixed interaction loop.

A central novelty lies in the unified evaluation of interactive segmentation under two complementary interaction regimes within a single task: a standardized simulated-interaction setting that enables scalable, reproducible benchmarking, and a clinician-driven interaction setting based on real expert scribbles that captures realistic human-AI correction behavior. All submissions are evaluated consistently across both regimes, allowing the challenge to study algorithmic adaptability under controlled conditions while simultaneously probing clinical

realism.

AutoPET V further advances the state of the art through the introduction of a fully new, harmonized, multi-center test cohort designed to stress generalization in clinically difficult scenarios. The test set deliberately includes diverse tracers, scanner configurations, heterogeneous disease burden, and a substantial proportion of lesion-absent or non-avid studies, addressing failure modes that have repeatedly emerged in prior challenge editions. By joining forces with related initiatives such as the DeepPSMA challenge, autoPET V harmonizes complementary PET/CT datasets and lessons learned across challenges to create a more robust and clinically representative benchmark. In contrast to earlier benchmarks, PET quantification is explicitly harmonized using QIBA-aligned SUV normalization, reducing acquisition-driven variability and enabling more meaningful cross-site performance comparisons.

On the evaluation side, autoPET V moves beyond single end-point accuracy metrics. Revised metric definitions disentangle semantic tumor burden estimation from instance-level lesion delineation and emphasize interaction efficiency, i.e., how rapidly and reliably models incorporate corrective input. This allows success to be defined not only by final segmentation quality, but also by responsiveness, robustness, and reduction of clinically relevant errors such as false positives from physiological uptake.

Beyond the task and evaluation design, autoPET V introduces a structured educational and reproducibility framework that consolidates methodological lessons learned from previous challenge editions. Participants are provided with interactive Jupyter notebook tutorials, reference data loaders, and explicit examples of interactive segmentation inputs, including the format and semantics of corrective scribbles. This infrastructure enables consistent interpretation of the task definition, encourages adoption of best practices, and supports fair comparison across diverse algorithmic approaches.

Together, these innovations establish autoPET V as a next-generation benchmark that reconceptualizes PET/CT lesion segmentation as a collaborative, adaptive process between algorithms and clinicians, rather than an isolated computational task.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

autoPET V defines a single unified task: interactive lesion segmentation in whole-body PET/CT. Participants develop algorithms that produce an initial automated segmentation of tracer-avid tumor lesions and iteratively refine this prediction in response to sparse corrective input during inference. The task reflects clinical practice, where automated results are selectively corrected by expert readers rather than manually redrawn.

Corrective input is provided in the form of sparse scribbles targeting false-positive and false-negative regions. At each interaction step, the algorithm must update its segmentation based on all previously provided input. The internal representation and handling of interaction are unconstrained, allowing participants to explore conditioning mechanisms, prompt-based approaches, or other interaction-aware architectures. Importantly, the interaction loop is designed to operate at inference time without retraining between steps, encouraging architectures that explicitly incorporate corrective input into their prediction pipeline.

The task is evaluated under two complementary interaction regimes, which define separate award categories while sharing a single task definition and executable: (1) iterative, error-driven simulation to approximate method-specific corrective behavior, and (2) clinically grounded interactions provided by medical annotators to ensure realism. In the standardized simulated-interaction regime, scribbles are generated in a controlled and reproducible manner to enable scalable quantitative benchmarking. In the clinician-driven interaction regime, real expert readers place scribbles based on clinical relevance, correcting all meaningful false positives and false

negatives without restrictions on placement or order. Each submission is evaluated under both regimes and is automatically eligible for both award categories.

Overall, the task emphasizes not only final segmentation accuracy but also adaptability and interaction efficiency, aiming to benchmark PET/CT algorithms that meaningfully support clinicians in realistic human-AI workflows.

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

N/A

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

2 Hours

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

N/A

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

We expect ~20 final submissions based on the previous challenges.

Final submissions: 21 (AutoPET I), 18 (AutoPET II), 21 (AutoPET III), 10 (AutoPET IV)

Registered participants: 273 (AutoPET I), 346 (AutoPET II), 612 (AutoPET III), 190 (AutoPET IV).

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

We aim to summarize the design, proposed methods, and results of the challenge in a manuscript to be submitted to a peer-reviewed scientific journal in the field of medical image analysis. To this end, we aim to invite the best-performing participants to contribute by describing their methods and experiences. Furthermore, the code of the best-performing methods will be made publicly available for the purpose of reproduction of results and further research.

MICCAI LNCS proceedings

Indicate if you want to offer MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings to the participants. Publishing a proceedings volume is optional and at the discretion of each challenge's organizers. At a minimum, organizers must ensure that a description of each participant's submission is publicly available. Organizers who wish to publish MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings must adhere to the MICCAI Satellite events publication process.

No

Collaboration with European Society of Radiology (ESR)

In collaboration with European Society of Radiology (ESR), we announce special clinical interest topics with associated clinicians who can help with the preparation of the proposals; the best 3 challenge proposals on these topics will get the opportunity to present their challenges at the European Congress of Radiology (ECR) 2027 in a special session. If you want to organize a challenge in collaboration with ESR on one of these topics, please reach out to the MICCAI Challenges Team ([miccai-challenges-2026@dkfz-heidelberg.de](mailto:micca-challenges-2026@dkfz-heidelberg.de)) and we will put you in contact with the corresponding clinician.

Challenge in collaboration with ESR. Ticking 'Yes' implies that the challenge has been prepared in collaboration with the clinical contact point.

Yes: AI-based assessment of PET imaging for oncology

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

grand-challenge.org is used as an online platform: NVIDIA T4 GPU (16 GB VRAM) with 8 CPUs and a max memory of 30 GB. Appropriate storage is associated with the deployed virtual machines.

TASK 1: Interactive PET/CT lesion segmentation

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Whole-body PET/CT is a cornerstone of oncologic imaging for staging, response assessment, and disease monitoring. Accurate delineation of tracer-avid tumor lesions is essential for quantitative analysis but remains a time-consuming and error-prone task in clinical routine. While recent advances in deep learning have enabled substantial progress in automated lesion segmentation, fully automatic approaches continue to struggle with heterogeneous lesion appearance, physiological tracer uptake, and domain shifts across centers and scanners. In clinical practice, automated predictions therefore require targeted human correction.

Task 1 of autoPET V addresses this gap by benchmarking interactive lesion segmentation in whole-body PET/CT. Participants develop algorithms that iteratively refine lesion segmentations in response to sparse corrective input provided during inference. Corrective input is represented as scribbles placed on false-positive and false-negative regions, reflecting minimal and clinically realistic user interactions. The task evaluates both the final segmentation quality and the efficiency with which algorithms incorporate additional guidance over successive interaction steps.

All submissions are evaluated under two complementary interaction regimes: a standardized simulated-interaction setting enabling scalable and reproducible benchmarking, and a clinician-driven setting based on real expert scribbles that captures realistic human-AI correction behavior. A single algorithm submission is used for both regimes.

By focusing on adaptability, robustness, and interaction efficiency rather than static end-point accuracy alone, Task 1 aims to advance PET/CT lesion segmentation toward clinically meaningful human-AI collaboration.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

PET/CT, PSMA, FDG, Tumor, Segmentation, Detection, Robustness, Interactive Segmentation, Human-in-the-loop

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Thomas Küstner (University Hospital Tübingen)

Sergios Gatidis (University Hospital Tübingen)

Ornela Megne (University Hospital Tübingen)

Felix Peisen (University Hospital Tübingen)

Michael Ingrisich (LMU Hospital Munich)

Matthias Fabritius (LMU Hospital Munich)

Jakob Dexeil (LMU Hospital Munich)

Katharina Jeblick (LMU Hospital Munich)
Clemens Cyran (LMU Hospital Munich)
Lalith Kumar Shiyam Sundar (LMU Hospital Munich)
Zdravko Marinov (KIT Karlsruhe)
Price Jackson (Peter MacCallum Cancer Centre)
Michael Hofman (Peter MacCallum Cancer Centre)
Jens Kleesiek (University Hospital Essen)
Moon Kim (University Hospital Essen)
Ken Herrmann (University Hospital Essen)

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Prof. Dr.-Ing. Thomas Küstner
University Hospital Tübingen
72076 Tübingen, Germany
E-mail: thomas.kuestner@med.uni-tuebingen.de

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Yes, they will provide guidance and be part of the interactive annotators for the test set

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Repeated event as open call challenge

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2026, ECR 2027

b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge.org

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your

responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

The challenge website will be opened on grand-challenge; similar to the previous challenges:

<https://autopet-v.grand-challenge.org/>

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

Fully automatic, Interactive

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

Publicly available data is allowed

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

We foresee the following awards for the best submissions in

Category 1: Simulated interactive lesion segmentation in PET/CT

1st Place: 1,500 €

2nd Place: 1,000 €

3rd Place: 500 €

Category 2: Clinician-driven interactive lesion segmentation in PET/CT

1st Place: 1,500 €

2nd Place: 1,000 €

3rd Place: 500 €

In the event of a tie the aggregate prize allocated for the tied positions shall be combined and equitably divided among the participants who share the identical ranking.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

All submissions will be reported in the leaderboard. Participating teams can opt out of publication of their results in the leaderboard. Prize-winning methods will be announced publicly as part of a scientific session at the MICCAI annual meeting.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

The prize-winning teams will be invited to contribute to draft and submit a manuscript describing the methods and results of the challenge in a peer-reviewed journal. The first and last author of the prize-winning submissions will be also listed as authors of this planned manuscript. The participating teams may publish their own results separately after coordination with the organizers to avoid significant overlap with the challenge paper.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Algorithms will be accepted as Docker containers according to the technical requirements of grand-challenge.org. Submission details will be published at the time point of challenge announcement.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

In order to enable participants to assess the technical compatibility of their to-be-submitted algorithm, we will provide information on successful algorithm deployment upon submission. To this end, the submitted algorithms will be applied to a small number of test data ensuring technical compatibility. This will allow participants to resubmit their algorithms in case of technical failure.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Challenge announcement and release of training cases: 03/2026

Registration: starting 04/2026

Submission deadline: 08/2026

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

For the already released FDG PET/CT dataset: The ethics committee of the University Hospital Tuebingen was consulted regarding the anonymized publication of training data. Ethical approval was obtained for the anonymized training database.

For the already released PSMA PET/CT dataset: The challenge dataset is provided in an anonymized fashion on the cancer imaging archive (TCIA), following the rigorous and well-established de-identification approach of TCIA. The institutional data security and privacy review board has approved the de-identification approach, and the institutional review board has waived the need for informed consent and approved the publication of the anonymized dataset (Ethics Committee, Medical Faculty, LMU Munich).

For the already released DeepPSMA dataset: Ethics approval is obtained from institutional review board. All image data is from patients who have previously consented to research use of image data. All images have been previously acquired and provided expert annotations from expert clinician staff members.

The test data used in autoPET V will not be publicly released. All test cases are derived from retrospective clinical PET/CT examinations collected at participating institutions. Ethical approval for retrospective analysis of these data exists at the respective sites, and all data are processed in anonymized form in accordance with local data protection regulations and applicable legal requirements. Test case labels and raw data are accessible only to a limited group of authorized challenge organizers and are used exclusively for evaluation purposes.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

Code for algorithm evaluation will be available at the time point of challenge submission on:
www.github.com/lab-midas/autoPETV

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Publication of algorithm code will be a prerequisite for award eligibility. To this end, code will need to be published on a publicly accessible repository of the teams choice within a week after submission deadline.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

This challenge is an initiative of the Radiology Departments of the University Hospitals of Tuebingen, LMU, Essen and Peter MacCallum Cancer Centre together with the European Society of Radiology (ESR) and the European Society for Hybrid, Molecular and Translational Imaging (ESHI-MT). We have secured funding for this challenge at BMBF (German Federal Ministry of Education and Research). We aim to additionally seek funding for this challenge from major companies in the field of medical imaging and data analysis. So far, no concrete sponsoring has been agreed on. Test cases and labels will only be available to a limited number of colleagues involved in organizing this challenge at the participating institutions.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

CAD, Research, Screening, Diagnosis

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Segmentation, Detection

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort consists of patients undergoing FDG and PSMA PET/CT examinations in an oncologic context for diagnosis, staging, or therapy response assessment, from multiple imaging sites.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The FDG PET/CT cohort comprises 1014 cases of 501 patients diagnosed with histologically proven malignant melanoma, lymphoma, or lung cancer, along with 513 negative control patients. The PSMA cohort includes pre-and/or post-therapeutic PET/CT images of male individuals with prostate carcinoma, encompassing images with (537) and without PSMA-avid tumor lesions (60). Notably, the training datasets exhibit distinct age distributions: the FDG PET/CT (UKT) cohort spans 570 male patients (mean age: 60y; std: 16y) and 444 female patients (mean age: 58y; std: 16y), whereas the PSMA PET/CT (LMU) cohort tends to be older, with 597 male patients (mean age: 71y; std: 8y). Additionally, there are variations in imaging conditions between the FDG (UKT) and PSMA (LMU) cohorts, particularly regarding the types and number of PET/CT scanners utilized for acquisition. The PSMA (LMU) dataset was acquired using three different scanner types (Siemens Biograph 64, Siemens Biograph 20 mCT and GE Discovery 690), whereas the FDG (UKT) dataset was acquired using a single scanner (Siemens Biograph mCT). In addition, autoPET V builds upon and aligns with the DeepPSMA challenge, which provides a large, curated multi-center cohort of whole-body PSMA PET/CT scans with expert-annotated prostate cancer lesions. The

DeepPSMA dataset captures a broad range of disease burden, physiological uptake patterns, and scanner configurations, and has been specifically designed to benchmark automated lesion segmentation under clinically challenging conditions. By integrating methodological insights and harmonization strategies from DeepPSMA, autoPET V further extends the diversity and robustness of PSMA PET/CT training resources and strengthens cross-challenge comparability.

Additional information about the PET/CT imaging protocols is provided in the section "Data acquisition details".

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

All PET/CT data within this challenge have been acquired on state-of-the-art PET/CT scanners using standardized protocols following international guidelines. CT as well as PET data are provided as 3D volumes consisting of stacks of axial slices.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

No additional information will be provided regarding the image data.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

age, sex

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The target and challenge cohort depict whole-body PET/CT imaging. Usually, the scan range of these examinations extends from the skull base to the mid-thigh level. If clinically relevant, scans can be extended to cover the entire body including the entire head and legs/feet. PSMA PET/CT training volumes are all acquired up to the skull base only.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The target structures of the to-be-developed algorithms are FDG- and PSMA-avid malignant tumors (i.e. primary tumors and metastases).

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy,Sensitivity,Specificity

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

PET/CT data were acquired on state-of-the-art PET/CT scanners (Siemens Biograph mCT, Siemens Biograph 64, Siemens Vision 600 PET/CT, GE Discovery 690, 710).

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Training data:

FDG dataset: Patients fasted at least 6 h prior to the injection of approximately 350 MBq 18F-FDG. Whole-body PET/CT images were acquired using a Biograph mCT PET/CT scanner (Siemens, Healthcare GmbH, Erlangen, Germany) and were initiated approximately 60 min after intravenous tracer administration. Diagnostic CT scans of the neck, thorax, abdomen and pelvis (200 reference mAs; 120 kV) were acquired 90 sec after intravenous injection of a contrast agent (90-120 ml Ultravist 370, Bayer AG) or without contrast agent (in case of existing contraindications). PET Images were reconstructed iteratively (three iterations, 21 subsets) with Gaussian post-reconstruction smoothing (2 mm full width at half-maximum). Slice thickness on contrast-enhanced CT was 2 or 3 mm.

PSMA dataset: Examinations were acquired on different PET/CT scanners (Siemens Biograph 64, Siemens Biograph 20 mCT and GE Discovery 690). The imaging protocol consisted of a diagnostic CT scan from the skull base to the mid-thigh using the following scan parameters: reference tube current exposure time product of around 140 mAs (mean); tube voltage of 100kV or 120 kV for most cases, slice thickness of 2.5 - 5 mm. Intravenous contrast enhancement was used in most studies, except for patients with contraindications. The whole-body PSMA-PET scan was acquired on average around 71 minutes after intravenous injection of 246 MBq 18F-PSMA (mean, 369 studies) or 214 MBq 68Ga-PSMA (mean, 228 studies), respectively. The PET data was reconstructed with attenuation correction derived from corresponding CT data using standard, vendor-provided image reconstruction algorithms (e.g. an ordered-subset expectation maximization (OSEM) algorithm) with a slice thickness ranging from 3 - 5 mm (mean: 3.5 mm).

DeepPSMA dataset: In addition, autoPET V aligns with the DeepPSMA challenge, which provides a multi-center whole-body PSMA PET/CT cohort acquired under clinically routine conditions for prostate cancer imaging. DeepPSMA data encompass scans from different PET/CT systems and PSMA tracers, with expert-annotated prostate cancer lesions and a wide range of disease burden and physiological uptake patterns. Imaging protocols and reconstruction follow standard clinical practice, enabling complementary coverage of PSMA-specific uptake characteristics and scanner variability. Methodological insights and harmonization strategies from DeepPSMA are

incorporated to strengthen robustness and cross-challenge comparability.

Test data: Test data in autoPET V consist of a fully new, unseen multi-center cohort (UKT, LMU, Peter MacCallum Cancer Centre, University Hospital Essen) designed to evaluate generalization and interaction robustness under clinically realistic conditions. The test set spans multiple PET tracers, scanner configurations, and acquisition environments, and deliberately includes a substantial proportion of lesion-absent or low-uptake studies as well as cases with pronounced physiological tracer uptake. In particular, the test cohort is designed to reflect clinically relevant diversity in radionuclide usage across participating centers, thereby introducing realistic tracer-dependent domain shifts relative to the established training data. This design aims to challenge both lesion detection sensitivity and false-positive suppression. To prevent fine-tuning to the test domain, detailed information on case composition including detailed information on tracer proportions and radionuclide-specific case counts, center contributions, and acquisition parameters will not be disclosed prior to the challenge deadline. Aggregate characteristics of the test cohort will be made public after completion of the challenge.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Data were acquired from large university hospitals (UKT, LMU, Peter MacCallum Cancer Centre, University Hospital Essen).

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Data were acquired by specialized teams consisting of radiologists, nuclear medicine physicians, and technologists. Manual segmentation of tumor lesions was performed by two radiologists with experience in hybrid imaging.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

A case (training or test case) consists of one 3D whole-body PET volume, one corresponding 3D whole-body CT volume and one 3D binary mask of manually segmented tumor lesions of the size of the PET volume. CT and PET were acquired simultaneously on a single PET/CT scanner in one session; thus PET and CT are anatomically aligned up to minor shifts due to physiological motion. A pre-processing script for resampling the PET and CT to the same matrix size will be provided.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Training cases: 1014 FDG PET/CT studies, 597 PSMA PET/CT studies, 100 DeepPSMA PET/CT studies.

Test cases: 200 FDG and PSMA PET/CT studies originating from UKT, LMU, Peter MacCallum Cancer Centre, University Hospital Essen.

Challenge participants are free to use additional external training data or pre-trained models as long as these are publicly available. If additional labels are generated in this process, these should be made publicly available by the participants after the challenge. The use of additional training data or models should be reported.

autoPET V does not provide a separate validation dataset. Participants are free to define their own validation strategies using the released training data, including cross-validation or hold-out splits, according to their methodological preferences. All final performance evaluation and ranking are performed exclusively on the held-out test data.

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

All training data is fully annotated. The test cases will be a newly compiled cohort with ~25% being already annotated.

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The number of training cases is a trade-off between the effort of manual lesion segmentation and the necessity for sufficient training data. To our knowledge this is the largest publicly available labeled whole-body PET/CT data set for FDG and PSMA tracers.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

All training cases are drawn from the hospitals: University Hospital Tuebingen (UKT), University Hospital Munich (LMU), Peter MacCallum Cancer Centre (Australia).

Test cases are split in four subgroups: UKT, LMU, Peter MacCallum Cancer Centre, University Hospital Essen

The rationale behind this selection of test cases is to assess the robustness of algorithms and to cross-evaluate the effects of center and tracer.

All training datasets include PET/CT examinations acquired across different clinical stages, including baseline staging, follow-up, and post-therapeutic assessments, reflecting routine clinical practice. For the challenge, data splitting is performed at the patient level, ensuring that no patient contributes studies to both training and test sets. Consequently, pre- and post-therapeutic examinations from the same patient are never split across training and test data.

The test set is constructed independently from the publicly released training data and includes a representative mix of pre-therapeutic, post-therapeutic, and treatment-response studies, with particular emphasis on clinically challenging scenarios such as partially treated lesions, heterogeneous uptake patterns, and low-contrast residual disease. This design intentionally exposes algorithms to therapy-induced appearance changes and domain shifts while preventing information leakage from longitudinal patient data.

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

Data of 1017 cases (autoPET I + II) and 597 cases (autoPET III) were previously released for training of the autoPET challenge series. Around 75% of new test cases will be compiled in this proposed challenge to reflect different

clinical scenarios.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

All data were manually annotated by two radiologists with experience in hybrid imaging. To this end, tracer-avid tumor lesions were manually segmented on the PET image data using dedicated software.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

FDG/PSMA PET/CT: The following annotation protocol was defined

Step 1: Identification of tracer-avid tumor lesions by visual assessment of PET and CT information together with the clinical examination reports.

Step 2: Manual free-hand segmentation of identified lesions in axial slices.

DeepPSMA: Manual annotation workflow described in: 1. Buteau JP, Martin AJ, Emmett L, Iravani A, Sandhu S, Joshua AM, et al. PSMA and FDG-PET as predictive and prognostic biomarkers in patients given [177Lu] Lu-PSMA-617 versus cabazitaxel for metastatic castration-resistant prostate cancer (TheraP): a biomarker analysis from a randomised, open-label, phase 2 trial. *The Lancet Oncology*. 2022;23(11):1389-97

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

FDG PET/CT training and test data from UKT was annotated by a Radiologist with >10 years of experience in hybrid imaging and experience in machine learning research.

FDG PET/CT test data from LMU was annotated by a radiologist with 9 years of experience in hybrid imaging.

PSMA PET/CT training and test data from the LMU as well as PSMA PET/CT test data from UKT was annotated by a single reader and reviewed by board-certified medical imaging experts with 4 years and >10 years of experience in hybrid imaging.

DeepPSMA: All images marked up by specialist nuclear medicine physicians with at least 5 years experience in clinical molecular imaging.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

For training and test data, original DICOM files will be anonymized and provided. In addition, scripts for conversion to the NIfTI format, for conversion of PET data from original image units (activity count) to standardized uptake values following QIBA standards, and for resampling the PET and CT to the same matrix size will be provided.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

One relevant possible error source for image annotation is the uncertainty for whether a tracer-avid lesion is actually malignant as this cannot always be determined by PET/CT alone. For experienced readers and regarding the tumor entities chosen in this challenge, a rough estimate of false classification of lesions in this sense is about 5-10%. The second relevant possible error source is the uncertainty of defining lesion boundaries, especially on PET data that have low intrinsic resolution. The difference in segmentation volumes can range from 5-30%.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

A further potential error source are image artifacts in PET and/or CT that may result in altered image properties.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

To assess algorithm performance in interactive PET/CT lesion segmentation, autoPET V employs a set of complementary metrics that jointly capture segmentation accuracy, lesion detection behavior, and interaction efficiency. The metrics are evaluated iteratively over the interaction process and summarized using area-under-the-curve (AUC) formulations to reflect how effectively algorithms incorporate corrective input.

At each interaction step, user inputs will be represented as scribbles targeting false positive and false negative regions, under two complementary regimes: (1) simulated, fully reproducible scribbles; and (2) clinician-provided scribbles contributed by practicing clinicians from every center. A total of 200 test cases will be evaluated using simulated scribbles, and 80 test cases will be evaluated using real clinician-provided scribbles.

Simulated interaction: For the simulated regime, we adopt three well-established scribble simulation protocols introduced in ScribblePrompt (ECCV 2024) and nInteractive (arXiv 2025). Scribbles are generated on the largest connected false positive or false negative component and include: (i) centerline scribbles placed along the medial axis of the component, (ii) contour scribbles drawn along the component boundary, and (iii) line scribbles

connecting two randomly selected points within the component. For each test case, one of these three simulation strategies is selected uniformly at random to reflect variability in annotator behavior. To ensure fair and reproducible comparisons across algorithms, the selected scribble type is fixed per test case (e.g., test case 002 is always evaluated using centerline scribbles across all methods). This ensures fairness and comparability across methods. Each case will undergo five successive scribble-based correction steps, providing a standardized interaction budget for all participants. The scribble simulation code will be released to participants, enabling them to reproduce identical human-in-the-loop corrections on additional data, for example, for method development or fine-tuning.

Clinician-driven interaction: In the second regime, scribbles will be provided by at least two real clinicians from every center (UKT, LMU, Peter MacCallum Cancer Centre, University Hospital Essen). Clinicians will be presented with PET/CT images overlaid with the segmentation output of the top-performing team from autoPET IV and will annotate regions they identify as under- or over-segmented by placing scribbles directly on the predicted mask. These clinician annotations will be stored as precomputed inputs and used during evaluation. Algorithms will receive the clinician-provided scribbles sequentially, following the same interaction protocol as in the simulated regime. Unlike the simulated setting, however, the number of scribbles per case will not be fixed (i.e., not necessarily five), but will instead reflect the clinician's judgment, as some cases may require more corrective input than others. Importantly, the same clinician scribbles will be used for all methods to ensure consistent and fair comparison. This design is motivated by our observation that segmentation errors across models from prior autoPET iterations substantially overlap. Most methods struggle with similar challenging cases (e.g., weak uptake or small-volume tumors). We therefore assume that corrections derived from a strong reference model identify informative regions that are broadly relevant for submissions to autoPET V while preserving realistic interaction patterns.

Post-challenge analyses of previous autoPET iterations have shown that models tend to make errors on largely overlapping lesion sets, typically small lesions with weak tracer uptake. We therefore expect that corrections derived from the best-performing approach in prior iterations will provide meaningful and realistic guidance for algorithms submitted to autoPET V. Moreover, using identical clinician-provided scribbles across all participants ensures that performance differences reflect algorithmic capabilities rather than variability in user input.

The primary evaluation metrics are:

1. **Dice Similarity Coefficient (Dice):** Dice is used to quantify voxel-wise overlap between predicted and reference lesion segmentations and reflects overall segmentation accuracy.
2. **Detection-Matching Metric (DMM):** To better capture lesion-level detection performance, an aggregated detection metric is introduced that evaluates the matching between predicted and reference lesion components. This metric explicitly accounts for both false-positive and false-negative lesion components and is designed to disentangle semantic tumor burden estimation from instance-level delineation accuracy. To avoid ambiguity with the Dice score, this metric is referred to as the Detection-Matching Metric (DMM).

For both Dice and DMM, values are computed at each interaction step and summarized as AUC-Dice and AUC-DMM, respectively, using the trapezoidal rule. The AUC formulation reflects interaction efficiency by measuring how rapidly segmentation performance improves as additional corrective input is provided. In the simulated setting, each case will undergo five successive scribble-based correction steps, providing a standardized interaction budget for all participants. For the real interactive setting, however, the number of

scribbles per case will not be fixed (i.e., not necessarily five), but will instead reflect the clinician's judgment, as some cases may require more corrective input than others. After challenge completion, we will release the clinician-provided scribble statistics for transparency.

In addition to the primary metrics used for ranking, the following quantities are reported for post-challenge analysis:

- Final Dice and Final DMM after the last interaction step
- False-positive volume (FPV)
- False-negative volume (FNV)

For lesion-absent test cases, detection-based metrics are evaluated accordingly to reflect false-positive suppression behavior.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The overarching objective of the present challenge is to develop robust methods for detecting and segmenting tracer-avid tumor lesions in whole-body PET/CT under clinically realistic conditions. While automated lesion segmentation has shown substantial progress in recent years, clinical practice remains characterized by targeted human correction of algorithmic predictions rather than fully automatic operation. Accordingly, the assessment metrics of autoPET V are designed to reflect both segmentation accuracy and the ability of algorithms to effectively incorporate sparse user guidance.

Post-challenge analyses of previous autoPET editions have demonstrated that voxel-level overlap measures alone are insufficient to fully characterize algorithm performance in PET/CT. In particular, false-positive segmentations arising from physiological tracer uptake and false-negative omissions of small or low-contrast lesions represent dominant clinical failure modes. Building on these insights, autoPET V retains Dice-based overlap evaluation while extending the assessment to explicitly capture lesion-level detection behavior and interaction efficiency.

Dice similarity is used as a measure of overall segmentation accuracy and continuity with previous autoPET challenges, enabling direct comparison across editions. To complement Dice and to better reflect lesion-level correctness, the Detection-Matching Metric (DMM) is introduced. DMM jointly accounts for false-positive and false-negative lesion components and disentangles semantic tumor burden estimation from instance-level lesion delineation, which is particularly relevant in cases with clustered lesions or heterogeneous uptake patterns.

Both Dice and DMM are evaluated iteratively over successive interaction steps and summarized using area-under-the-curve (AUC) formulations. The AUC-based evaluation captures interaction efficiency, i.e., how rapidly and reliably an algorithm improves its predictions as additional corrective input becomes available. This formulation reflects realistic clinical usage, where the goal is to achieve clinically acceptable segmentations with minimal interaction effort rather than only optimizing the final outcome.

In addition to the AUC-based primary metrics used for ranking, final Dice and DMM values, as well as false-positive and false-negative volumes, are reported for post-challenge analysis. These complementary measures enable detailed investigation of algorithm behavior, common failure modes, and trade-offs between sensitivity and specificity across tracers, centers, and interaction regimes.

The dual interactive regime (simulation and clinician) provide a balanced and scalable evaluation framework that combines clinical plausibility with model-specific corrective behavior. The simulated regime enables scalable, submission-specific refinement and reproducible benchmarking. The clinician-driven regime ensures clinical realism and captures expert correction patterns.

Clinicians will be presented with PET/CT images overlaid with the segmentation output of the top-performing team from autoPET IV and asked to correct the model's errors by placing scribbles directly on the predicted mask. They will be instructed to focus on clinically relevant discrepancies, including: (1) over- and under-segmentation of detected lesions; (2) entirely missed lesions; and (3) false-positive anatomical uptake incorrectly identified as lesions.

This provides general guidance on what types of errors to correct, while remaining sufficiently broad to avoid enforcing a rigid or overly standardized annotation protocol. The intention is to capture natural corrective behavior rather than systematically covering all possible variabilities, thereby reducing the risk of introducing annotation bias.

While simulated scribbles lack certain clinical nuances and clinician scribbles are fixed across methods, their combination provides a scalable and method-agnostic evaluation.

Overall, the chosen metrics align with the clinical objectives of PET/CT lesion assessment and support a comprehensive evaluation of accuracy, robustness, and adaptability in interactive human-AI workflows.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

Only the best submission by each participating team will be considered. We will use the well-established rank-then-aggregate strategy as the ranking scheme.

Step 1 (Compute): For each test case, AUC-Dice (higher is better) and AUC-DMM (higher is better) are computed.

Step 2 (Rank): Submissions are ranked separately per metric and per test case.

Step 3 (Aggregate): The final ranking score for each submission is obtained by averaging ranks across all test cases and both metrics, with equal weighting (50% AUC-Dice, 50% AUC-DMM).

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Submissions with missing results on test cases will not be considered for the leaderboard.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

This ranking strategy emphasizes both accurate segmentation and effective lesion detection while explicitly rewarding efficient utilization of interactive input. All submissions are evaluated using the same metrics under both interaction regimes (simulated and clinician-driven), enabling consistent comparison and category-specific award determination.

The rank-then-aggregate strategy was chosen because it provides a robust and fair framework for evaluating and comparing the performance of models across diverse test cases and metrics. This method has been

well-established in the evaluation of segmentation challenges, ensuring consistency and reproducibility in the ranking process. By separating evaluation into distinct steps — computing metrics, ranking teams for each metric, and aggregating results — this approach mitigates potential biases arising from differences in scale or distribution between metrics, which we have observed in previous iterations of the autoPET challenge. The use of ranking normalizes performance comparisons, making them less sensitive to outliers or variations in absolute metric values across test cases.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

For each submission, the mean and standard deviation of all reported metrics are computed across the test cohort. Metric distributions and rank variability are analyzed to assess robustness across centers, tracers, and interaction regimes. Missing or incomplete submissions are excluded from ranking.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

The precision of performance estimates for individual algorithms is assessed by reporting the mean and standard deviation of all primary metrics (AUC-Dice and AUC-DMM) across the test cohort. In addition, non-parametric bootstrap resampling over test cases (e.g. 1000 replicates) is performed to estimate 95% confidence intervals of mean performance measures, providing an uncertainty estimate without assuming normality of the metric distributions.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across tests cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

Variability of algorithm performance across test cases is assessed using descriptive statistics, including standard deviation and interquartile range (IQR) of per-case metric values. Metric distributions are analyzed separately for relevant subgroups, such as tracer type, center, lesion burden, and interaction regime, to identify systematic performance differences and common failure modes. Outlier cases are inspected qualitatively as part of the post-challenge analysis.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

Ranking variability is assessed by analyzing the stability of rank positions across test cases and metrics within the rank-then-aggregate framework. Sensitivity analyses may be performed by evaluating rankings under alternative aggregation orders (e.g. per-metric or per-center aggregation) to assess robustness of the final leaderboard. These analyses aim to identify whether rankings are driven by consistent performance or dominated by a small subset of cases.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

The primary goal of the challenge is benchmarking rather than formal hypothesis testing. Accordingly, statistical significance testing between algorithms is not used to determine the official ranking. Where pairwise comparisons are performed for exploratory or post-challenge analyses, non-parametric tests (e.g. paired Wilcoxon signed-rank

tests across test cases) may be employed, given the non-Gaussian nature of segmentation metrics. Results of such analyses are reported descriptively and interpreted cautiously.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

Submissions with missing or invalid outputs for one or more test cases are excluded from ranking. Partial results are not imputed. For statistical summaries beyond ranking, only valid test cases for a given submission are considered, and the number of evaluated cases is reported to ensure transparency.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

All statistical analyses are performed using standard scientific computing software, including Python-based libraries such as NumPy, SciPy, and pandas. Visualization and exploratory analyses are conducted using established plotting libraries. Evaluation scripts and ranking procedures are made publicly available to ensure transparency and reproducibility.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

In addition to ranking, further analyses include evaluation of false-positive and false-negative behavior, interaction convergence characteristics, inference runtime, and qualitative assessment of correction patterns under clinician-driven interaction. These analyses aim to identify common strengths, failure modes, and emerging best practices in interactive PET/CT lesion segmentation.

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

Gatidis S, Hepp T, Fruh M, La Fougère C, Nikolaou K, PfannenberG C, Schölkopf B, Kustner T, Cyran C, Rubin D. A whole-body FDG-PET/CT Dataset with manually annotated Tumor Lesions. *Sci Data*. 2022 Oct 4;9(1):601. doi: 10.1038/s41597-022-01718-3. PMID: 36195599; PMCID: PMC9532417.

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Ma, Jun, et al. "Unleashing the strengths of unlabelled data in deep learning-assisted pan-cancer abdominal organ quantification: the FLARE22 challenge." The Lancet Digital Health 6.11 (2024): e815-e826

<https://github.com/lab-midas/autoPET>

<https://autopet.grand-challenge.org/>

<https://autopet-ii.grand-challenge.org/>

<https://autopet-iii.grand-challenge.org/>

<https://autopet-iv.grand-challenge.org/>

<https://www.autopet.org>

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

While the autoPET datasets constitute the largest publicly available collection of expert-annotated whole-body PET/CT data across multiple tracers and centers, we acknowledge that the current scale is not sufficient to train standalone foundation models from scratch. The primary objective of autoPET V is therefore not foundation model training, but benchmarking robustness, generalization, and interactive adaptation in clinically realistic workflows. Notably, data from previous autoPET editions have already been successfully used together with other databases for training of large foundation models, including MedSAM-based architectures. We plan to further expand the dataset in future autoPET iterations to progressively support larger-scale model development.